

SYBILSECURE: AN ENERGY EFFICIENT SYBIL ATTACK DETECTION TECHNIQUE IN WIRELESS SENSOR NETWORK

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ABSTRACT:

A wireless sensor network consists of many sensor nodes which are deployed to monitor physical or environmental conditions and to pass the collected data to a base station. Though wireless sensor network is subjected to have major applications in all the areas, it also has many security threats and attacks. Among all threats such as sinkhole, wormhole, selective forwarding, denial of service and node replication, Sybil attack is a major attack where a single node has multiple identities. When a Sybil node act as a sender, it can send false data to its neighbors. When it acts as receiver, it can receive the data which is originally destined for a legitimate node. The existing solutions consume more energy. So an energy efficient algorithm named Sybilsecure is proposed. Experimental results show that Sybilsecure consumes less energy than existing defense mechanisms.

KEYWORDS:

Wireless sensor network, Sybil, cluster head, query packet.

1. INTRODUCTION:

Wireless sensor networks consist of as many numbers of nodes which can communicate with each other. Each node consists of a microcontroller, an electronic circuit for interfacing with sensors and battery, a radio transceiver and an external memory. Wireless sensor networks are being used for various applications such as area monitoring, healthcare monitoring and monitoring the combat zone for security purposes. But due to the broadcast nature in wireless communication and low physical protection of sensor nodes, an intruder can easily tend to attack the network. Various attacks on each layer are listed in the table below.

Table 1. Attacks on different layers

Layer	Attack
Physical	Jamming , Node destruction
Data link	Denial of service
Network	Spoofing, replaying, Hello floods, Homing ,Sybil
Transport	SYN flood , De synchronization attack
Application	Reprogramming attacks

In this paper, an efficient algorithm against Sybil attack is proposed as it is a huge destructive attack in sensor networks. In case of Sybil attack, a sensor node behaves as if it were a larger number of nodes, by faking other nodes. Sybilsecure is based on the querying and acknowledging the nodes.

2. RELATED WORK:

The existing mechanisms include centralized and decentralized approaches. The vast implemented solution is trusted certification [12],[13]. This solution assumes that there is a special trusted third party or central authority, which can verify the validity of each participant, and further issues a certification for the honest one. In reality, such certification can be a special hardware device or a digital number. Note that essentially both of them are a series of digits, but are stored on different media. Before a participant joins a peer-to-peer system, provides votes, or obtains services from the system, first his identity must be verified. This method gets its limitation when it is applied for larger network. Another method works based on the resource used by the node. If a Sybil node exists then it has to perform the tasks of the identities it possess. So when it exceeds a threshold value then the Sybil node is detected. [14]. Secret key [15] can also be shared but it consumes more power as it involves in complex encryption and decryption techniques. In contrast to existing solutions that are based on sharing encryption keys, RSSI based scheme [16] presents a solution for Sybil attack based on received signal strength indicator (RSSI) readings of messages. Though it is said to be lightweight (i.e., only one message communication), it is time-varying, unreliable and radio transmission is non-isotropic. Accuracy reduces as the transmission distance increases. Recent researches in Sybil defense mechanisms are based on Social network based schemes [1] [2] [3] [4] [8] [10] [13] [14]. These schemes use the trust structure embodied in the networks. They have two assumptions, 1) Sybil nodes can create arbitrarily number of identities but relationship to non-Sybil nodes. Sybil nodes are poorly connected to non-Sybil nodes. 2) One trusted non-Sybil node is known. Based on these assumptions various defense schemes such as Sybilguard, Sybillimit, Sybilcontrol , Sybilinfer , Sumup, Gatekeeper are proposed.

3. PROPOSED WORK:

The proposed solution is based on sending and responding to the query sent by the cluster head. The Cluster head has a list of its sub nodes parameters. The parameters are the identities and their location.

Fig.1. Network with a Cluster head, 4 legitimate nodes and a Sybil node.

Table 2. Dataset in Cluster head

NODE	DATASET
	1,X
	2,Y
	3,Z
	4,A

The Cluster head broadcasts a query packet to all the sub nodes in such a way that it expects a reply that all the sub nodes must send their id and location. There are three cases in which the Sybil node reacts.

(i) No reply:

When a query packet is received by all the legitimate sub nodes including Sybil node, it does not respond to it. It simply gets the packet and drops it. Whenever retransmission is done for multiple times, the Sybil node does not respond to it.

(ii) Replies with same Identity and different coordinates:

In this case, all the legitimate sub nodes respond to the cluster head with their identity and location. The Sybil node also responds to the cluster head with any one of the Sub nodes identity

and its own location. For example, If a cluster head has 4 nodes say 1,2,3,4 with the location x, y, z, a respectively, Sybil node must have any one these identity (1/2/3/4) and its own location d. Now the Sybil node responds with any one of these identities and the location d. The cluster head already has the set of legitimate nodes identity and location. Conflicts arise when the legitimate node and Sybil node has same and different location. The node with the different location is detected as Sybil node.

Table 3. Acknowledgements received

NODE	ID	LOCATION
	1	X
	2	Y
	3	Z
	4	A
	1/2/3/4	B

(iii) Replies with same identity and same coordinates:

This case will be future scope of this paper.

4. ENERGY CALCULATION:

In wireless sensor network energy consumption is a major factor. Because when a node runs out of battery, it becomes a major problem in network. A dead node will affect entire communication. So the energy consumed by the network to detect a Sybil node is calculated. Based on the formulae from [17], the energy values are calculated. Equations (1) and (2) show the energy for cluster head and a node respectively.

$$E_N(ij) = b V_{sup} I_{sense} T_{sense} + b V_{sup} (I_{write} T_{write} + I_{read} T_{read}) + b E_{elec} + B d_{ij}^n E_{amp} + T_A V_{sup} [C_N I_A + (1-C_N)I_S] \dots (1)$$

$$ECH(j) = h_3 b V_{sup} I_{sense} T_{sense} + h_4 V_{sup} (I_{write} T_{write} + I_{read} T_{read}) + h_1 b_1 N_{CYC} C_{avg} V_{SUP}^2 (n_j+1) + h_1 b_1 V_{sup} (I_0 e^{(V_{sup}/N_p VT)} (N_{CYC}/f) (n_j+1) + h_2 b_1 E_{elec} (n_j) + h_2 b_2 (1 + \gamma) d_j^n E_{amp} + h_2 \gamma b_2 E_{elec} + T_{CH} V_{sup} [C_{CH} I_A + (1-C_{CH})I_S] + E_{actu} N_{act} \dots (2)$$

Consider a network which has a cluster head and four nodes. The tables below show the energy consumed by cluster head and sensor node.

Table 4. Energy consumed by cluster head

Cluster head	Energy Consumed (J)
Transmit	0.00784
Transient	0.049
Sense	0.594
Data logging	0.0000385
Receive	0.00384

Table 5. Energy consumed by each node

Sensor node	Energy consumed
Transmit	0.00088
Transient	0.012
Sense	0.54
Data logging	0.000035
Receive	0.00349

Upon simulation Sybilsecure takes about 11.327 J to detect a Sybil node. But when considering other social based defense schemes such as Sybilguard and Sybillimit consumes more energy than Sybilsecure. Sybillimit consumes around 8.8 J for a period of time. Sybilguard consumes about 13.48 J for a single round.

5. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND COMPARISONS:

Fig 2. Energy consumed to detect Sybil nodes.


```
ex Turbo C++ IDE
Enter the Cluster head id1
Enter the position of Cluster head11
21
Enter the number of nodes3
Enter the ids of the nodes2
3
4
5
Enter the xpos of the nodes12
13
14
15
Enter the ypos of the nodes22
23
24
25
Sending query packets from cluster head to nodes
Acknowledgegment of Query packets
Verfying the ids
verify the position of the nodes
No node is sybil
```

Fig 3. Absence of Sybil node


```
ex Turbo C++ IDE
Enter the Cluster head id1
Enter the position of Cluster head11
21
Enter the number of nodes3
Enter the ids of the nodes2
3
8
5
Enter the xpos of the nodes12
13
14
15
Enter the ypos of the nodes22
23
24
25
Sending query packets from cluster head to nodes
Acknowledgegment of Query packets
Verfying the ids
Node 3 is suspicious
```

Fig 4. Presence of Sybil node

6. CONCLUSION:

In this paper, Sybilsecure, an energy efficient algorithm is proposed based on sending and acknowledging the query data packets. Social network based schemes which involved in random

routes of data consumed more energy to detect a Sybil node. But in Sybilsecure , a Sybil node can be detected with less energy and also without decreasing its efficiency.

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